

PHYSICAL AND THERMAL DEGRADATION OF THERMOPLASTIC MATRICES FOR HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The thermal stability and solvent resistance of thermoplastic matrices such as Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) and Polyetherimide (PEI) is evaluated. An original kinetic model is proposed and verified for the thermal degradation of PEEK. Moreover, accelerated degradation have been used to predict long term stability of PEEK and PEI and the model confirmed the experimental data. The environmental resistance of PEEK and PEI films has been evaluated in terms of variation of the mechanical properties after exposure to aircraft industry solvents. The results of the morphological and environmental resistance characterization, together with the degradation studies demonstrate the good stability of PEEK and the higher tendency of the amorphous PEI to reduce its mechanical properties after solvent exposure.

KEYWORDS: Thermoplastic composite, thermal degradation, solvent resistance

INTRODUCTION

The characterization of the behavior of a composite that is utilized in aeronautic supersonic transport under critical temperature conditions, implies the knowledge of both the thermal degradation behavior and the resistance to aeronautic solvents. In order to select a material which properties must be guaranteed for a determined lifetime, parameters such as solvent resistance and degradation behavior must be considered as design parameters. Thermoplastic matrices such as PEEK and PEI are considered candidate materials for this kind of applications. In particular a process used to perform the welding of thermoplastic PEEK composites implies the use of an amorphous PEI film as interply (1). Reported advantages offered by such technique include a preservation of dimensional tolerance and fiber orientation in the vicinity of the weld interface and a limitation of the probable degradation of PEEK by successive remelting cycles. Moreover, the lower temperature involved in the bonding process and the limited depth of the melted zone allow significant time and cost reductions and guarantee good mechanical properties (1). On the other hand, a potential problem is represented by the lower resistance to aeronautic solvents and service fluids as a consequence of the amorphous nature of the bonding layers. It has been reported, in fact, that PEI can undergo modification of its properties if exposed to aircraft industry solvents for a long time (2).

The degradation of polymeric composites has been studied in relation with the reprocessability of thermoplastics after several cycles (3-5). For example, PEEK changes its attitude to crystallize if it is repetitively heated up to 400°C, indicating physical degradation. The weight loss occurring to a polymer that is kept at high temperatures for a certain amount of time is considered another index of degradation. Such a weight loss can be attributed to evaporation of solvents and/or plasticizers or to chain decomposition. Moreover, (6-8) the mechanisms of

degradation are function of the polymer structure and can follow different steps because of the complexity of polymeric chains. Functional group transfer, chain unzipping with elimination of volatiles, and formation of intermediate compounds are the main decomposition mechanisms that contributes to complicate the development of a mechanistic kinetic model of the polymer degradation process. In particular, reported data on PEEK degradation indicated benzoquinone as first gaseous product of the chain breaking reaction followed by the rearranging of the polymer chain (8).

The effect of the environment is very important in polymer degradation as thermal oxidation is one of the major causes of polymer degradation. The presence of oxygen as reactant combined with heat causes very rapid degradation processes in the polymeric chains. Therefore its very important to fix the environmental condition when the decomposition kinetics are studied.

In the particular case of polymer based composites degradation the presence of the carbon fibers should also be taken into account. Carbon fibers, in fact, can affect the degradation process and degrade themselves in presence of oxygen. Furthermore in presence of degradation reactions where the diffusion in the bulk is the controlling step, the presence of carbon fibers can significantly affect the overall process.

Two methods to characterize the degradation of PEEK are considered in this work, the first is based on the modeling of the degradation reaction kinetic the other is based on an extrapolation of short term experiments to long times. Results of the reaction kinetics are used to confirm the test of accelerated degradation. Furthermore a series of tests are presented in order to evaluate the effect of solvents on the mechanical properties of PEEK and PEI matrices.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Thermal degradation studies have been performed using a TA Thermogravimetric Analyzer (TGA) model 911. Tests were performed in isothermal and dynamic modes at different temperatures and heating rates in order to cover a wide range of thermal conditions. Data obtained from TGA experiments were transformed in ASCII format and analyzed using a statistics computer program. TGA tests were performed, both in air and in nitrogen, on APC2 (ICI) thermoplastic matrix composites reinforced with AS4 carbon fibers and on PEI matrix carbon fiber composite (CETEX®). PEEK is a semicrystalline thermoplastic polymer that has been specially developed for high performance composites (9). It has a Tg of 147°C and a processing temperature of 400°C. On the other hand PEI is an amorphous thermoplastic matrix with a Tg of 210°C and a processing temperature of 320°C.

The solvent resistance of unreinforced PEEK and PEI in terms of weight gain and variation of the tensile strength versus time was then evaluated. Rectangular specimens of the neat matrices were cut from films of 0.1 mm. thickness. Another set of samples was prepared for the mechanical analysis according with ASTM D638-86. All the samples were immersed in skydrol and methylethylketone (MEK), chosen as typical aircraft fluids, at 25°C and 70°C up to 30 days. For both conditions the weight gain and the variation of the tensile strength was recorded as a function of exposure time. Tensile tests were performed with an Instron 4204 screw machine equipped with a load cell of 5 kN.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermal degradation studies

A typical TGA test performed in nitrogen is reported in Fig 1 where the weight loss of the PEEKmatrix composite is reported as a function of temperature at three different heating rates. The effect of the heating rate on the degradation kinetics is manifested in the shift of Fig. 1 curves: higher heating rate curves are shifted at higher degradation temperatures. This effect is mainly dependent on the activation energy of the degradation process. These tests have been also performed in air and the corresponding thermogram is shown in Fig. 2. The main difference observed between tests performed in nitrogen and air is that a complete degradation of the material is achieved in air while only the matrix is degraded in a carbonization process when working with nitrogen. This difference is also manifested by the shape of the derivative curve also shown in Figs. 1 and 2. A single peak characterizes the degradation reaction under nitrogen while a double peak is associated with the process in oxygen. In the second case the first peak is located in the same range of temperature and weight loss that the one observed in nitrogen, and can be attributed to the matrix degradation, while the second peak can be easily

attributed to the oxidation of the carbon fibers and the carbon structure of the degraded matrix. Apart from this difference no other differences are observed when working in different environments. A similar weight loss and temperature degradation interval characterizes the degradation of the matrix in both cases suggesting that the degradation of the matrix is given mainly by thermally controlled dehydrogenation without strong influence of oxidation processes on the reaction yield. However, the similarities between matrix degradation in nitrogen and air are only qualitative and a careful kinetic analysis should be performed to fully characterize the degradation behavior. This analysis will be facilitated when performed on the single peak reaction obtained for nitrogen environment tests.

Fig 1, dynamic TGA tests in Nitrogen for PEEK

Fig. 2, dynamic TGA test in air

While dynamic test results shown in Figs. 1 and 2 give useful information on the temperature interval and total weight loss associated with the degradation reactions; isothermal test results are needed for kinetic analysis in order to decouple the contribution of temperature. An isothermal test in nitrogen at 480 °C is shown in Fig. 3 .

Fig. 3, Isothermal TGA test at 480 °C

The good thermal stability of the PEEK matrix composite is reflected in the long time scale needed to complete the degradation in nitrogen atmosphere. A typical experiment performed near 500 °C lasts for about 24 hours leading to a practical impossibility to perform experiments under controlled conditions in the region of interest (100 °C-250 °C). Therefore, other procedures should be followed in order to predict long time behavior of these materials under service conditions.

In order to apply a kinetic model, the degree of degradation was calculated from isothermal and dynamic tests in air as:

$$\alpha = (M_0 - M) / (M_0 - M_f) \quad (1)$$

Where M , M_0 and M_f are the actual, initial and final sample weights respectively. A kinetic model can be commonly expressed (5) in the following general form:

$$d\alpha/dt = K(T) f(\alpha) \quad (2)$$

where the temperature dependence of the kinetic constant can be expressed with an Arrhenius expression:

$$K = K_0 \exp(-E/RT) \quad (3)$$

where E is the activation energy of the degradation process. The form of the function $f(\alpha)$ depends on the form of the isothermal TGA thermogram. In particular, the form of the derivative peaks in Fig 3 suggests that the degradation process of PEEK follows a kinetics similar to that of the so-called autocatalytic reactions governed by the following model:

$$d\alpha/dt = K(T) \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (4)$$

where m and n are reaction orders. In agreement with experimental results, Eq. 4 predicts zero reaction rate at both ends of the process ($\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$).

The model parameters have been calculated using a non linear regression program; the comparison of model and experimental results, in terms of degree of degradation, for the isothermal tests is reported in Fig. 4. The model application to the dynamic tests present some discrepancies in the final part of the degradation process, but for durability studies only the first part of the degradation process, where the model gives an acceptable prediction, should be considered.

Fig. 4, model prediction and experimental data for the isothermal degradation of PEEK

Fig. 5 accelerated tests for PEEK

Fig. 6, accelerated test for PEI

Accelerated tests were also performed on both PEEK and PEI. A weight loss of 1% and 2% was considered as a threshold of the good performance of the material. In the hypothesis of such small weight loss it can be assumed, from Eq. 4, that this time varies with the temperature

according with:

$$t = \alpha^{(1-m)/(1-m)} \exp(E/RT) \quad (5)$$

Then, plotting $\ln(t)$ vs. $1/T$ the experimental values must lay on a straight line as shown in Figs. 5 and 6 where these values are plotted for PEEK and PEI for both levels of weight loss (1% and 2%) and for degradation in air and nitrogen. A simple linear regression allows the extrapolation to lower temperatures. The result of such analysis confirmed the excellent thermal stability of PEEK and PEI.

Solvent resistance

Films of PEI and PEEK were cut in a dumbbell shape and were immersed in MEK and skydrol for several days, at ambient temperature and at 70°C. Samples were periodically weighted and mechanically tested according with ASTM D638-86 and the weight gain was calculated as $(W-W_0)/W_0$ where W is the actual weight and W_0 is the initial weight. Solvent absorption results confirm the good stability of PEEK at ambient temperature, with an equilibrium weight gain lower than 0.2% while at 70°C the final weight gain is 0.8%. Such a low weight gain, however, can affect sensibly the mechanical properties as reported in Fig. 7 where the variation of the tensile strength of the PEEK film is shown as a function of the absorption time. A solvent content of 0.8% causes a diminution of the 20% of the modulus. Similar tests were performed on the PEI film. In this case a lower solvent resistance is observed with respect to the semicrystalline matrix, especially at high temperatures. The diminution of the modulus and the percent weight gain as function of time for PEI immersed in MEK is reported in Fig. 8 where it can be observed that the tensile strength decreases up to 40 % of its initial value. It should be pointed out that the PEEK film used in this work was a quenched grade, with almost a complete amorphous morphology like the PEI material. Evidently, a crystalline sample would have shown a higher stability (10).

The solvent absorption results were also analyzed in terms of the diffusion mechanism governing the process. Logarithmic plots of the weight gain versus the logarithm of time for both materials showed a linear correlation with exponents close to one. This behavior, typical of Case II diffusion that combines diffusion in the glassy region with swelling (10), was more evident in PEI (exponent = 1.1) than in PEEK (exponent = 0.8), indicating a lower degree of swelling in the PEEK film. This difference can be also expressed in terms of the different T_g of both materials considering that, as a general rule, the material with higher T_g shows a higher Case II behavior. Finally, with respect to the absorption conditions it should be noted that such environmental conditions are more severe than the actual service condition.

Experimental results obtained for immersion on skydrol showed a similar behavior that the one observed for MEK immersion, for both materials, with lower solvent absorption and reduction of mechanical properties.

Fig 7. Tensile strenght versus holding time for PEEK in MEK at two temperatures

Fig 8. Environmental behavior of PEI in MEK at 70°C

CONCLUSIONS

The thermal stability and solvent resistance of PEEK and PEI have been evaluated. A model similar to the one used for autocatalytic reaction was applied successfully to the degradation kinetics of PEEK. The model describes correctly the first part of the degradation process that can be considered as an indication of the material durability. Accelerated tests confirmed the excellent stability of these materials.

Solvent resistance experiments in aeronautic industry solvents showed that PEEK absorbs a smaller amount of MEK at ambient temperature respect to PEI. However, such small amount has a strong effect on the mechanical properties of such materials.

Both thermal stability test and environmental resistance confirmed the good performance of PEEK and PEI as matrices of high performance materials. However their range of application must be defined as a function of their thermal and environmental resistance.

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